

THE THEME OF LOYALTY AND LOVE IN ZULFIYA'S LYRICS

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information about Zulfiyaxanim's lyrics. In addition, the topic and idea of the poetess's poems and her poems about loyalty and love are analyzed.

Introduction.

Zulfiya Isroilova is a beloved, well-known, and talented poetess of the Uzbek people. Being the wife of the Uzbek poet Hamid Olimjon, Zulfiya won the hearts of millions of people through her creative work. Her poems have been recognized not only in our country but also worldwide. The poetess's works have been translated into many languages of the world, including Russian, English, German, Hindi, Chinese, Arabic, Persian, and others. For her poems on Indian themes, she was awarded the international Jawaharlal Nehru Prize. The talented poetess created works in various genres: epics, ballads, short stories, essays, poems, and a number of journalistic articles. Many of her poems are dedicated to the themes of peace and friendship. For her works glorifying peace and friendship, as well as for her active participation in the movement of Asian and African writers, she was awarded the international "Nilufar" Prize. During the war years, she wrote poems reflecting patriotic ideas. Zulfiya's hopeful poems such as "My Homeland," "With a Weapon in My Hand and a Greatcoat on My Back," and "Wait for Us" are considered among the works that express the militant spirit of Uzbek poetry of the war period. In addition, Zulfiya continuously enriched her lyrics with diverse and new images.

Main Part.

Zulfiya is rightly regarded as a symbol of spring, love, and the power of loyalty in Uzbek poetry. Indeed, the life of the poetess serves as an exemplary model for every Uzbek woman. The fate of Uzbek women occupies an important place in her creative work. In her poems, Zulfiya openly sang about the happiness and concerns of Uzbek women and girls. The poetess never tires of glorifying feminine grace in her poetry. In Zulfiya's works, we encounter love and compassion for nature and humanity. She depicts nature through various colors and symbols. Among the people, poems such as "Spring Came Asking for You," "My Son, There Must Be No War," "Without You," "Heart," and "Mushoira" are widely popular. It is well known that Zulfiya is a symbol of loyalty and love. After the death of her husband, themes of longing

and separation became dominant in her poetry. However, the poetess did not surrender to this bitter trial of life; instead, she found courage within herself, continued to create, and became a true symbol of loyalty. Alongside her creative activity, Zulfiya raised her children and continued the work of Hamid Olimjon. Living a lifetime in devotion, the poetess expressed her boundless loyalty, dedication, and love for Hamid Olimjon in poems such as “When the Apricot Blossoms,” “Have My Eyes Ever Seen Tears Like This?” and

“I Search!”

I know I will not find him.

After all, when did I ever lose him myself?

On the days my children and grandchildren were born,

Each time, I found him in Eternity...

Now, let us turn to Zulfiya’s poem titled “Where Are You, My Heart?”

Where have you gone, my heart,

My patience and endurance are exhausted.

To speak with you is my only wish,

My tongue is layered with sorrow upon sorrow.

This poem was written after the death of Hamid Olimjon, and it reflects the emotions of a woman suffering from the pain of separation. Since the content of the poem is filled with grief, its tone is also sorrowful. Everyone who reads Zulfiya’s poems can feel how profound her love for her life partner was and how deeply she suffered after his death. However, despite the short life she shared with her husband, she did not lose her loyalty to her family and her life companion for many long years.

Conclusion.

Zulfiyaxonim holds a unique place in Uzbek poetry. It would not be an exaggeration to say that she was a woman who embodied all noble human qualities. Even during the period of independence, Zulfiya’s creative legacy—her poems and literary works—has been further honored and celebrated. In 2004, the Zulfiya State Prize was established in our country. This award is presented to girls who have achieved success in literature, art, and other fields.

Today, the life and creative work of Zulfiya can serve as an example for all women. Her diligence, loyalty as a devoted spouse, constant aspiration to move forward, and her spirit of inquiry inspire admiration in the hearts of women. Even now, her poems continue to be recited on platforms around the world. Her exemplary life and unique talent remain a role model for the younger generation.

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